

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

ADT41 (JJ92), a short-duration Basmati rice for Tamil Nadu, India

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Basmati rices are reputed for their aroma and quality. Traditional Basmati rices are tall, low-yielding, photoperiod-sensitive, and susceptible to insect pests, diseases, and lodging. High-yielding Basmati varieties are cultivated in northwestern India.

ADT41, popularly known as JJ92, is a semidwarf Basmati developed at Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TNRRI), Aduthurai. It is a selection from a dwarf mutant of Basmati 370. It matures early (110 d), has acceptable Basmati rice quality, and is nonlodging and photoperiod-insensitive. It is moderately resistant to blast but susceptible to brown planthopper, leafhopper, bacterial blight, and bacterial leaf streak.

ADT41 yielded a mean of 4.2 t/ha in 44 trials at research stations and on farms (Table 1). The highest grain yield obtained was 10.6 t/ha in the Adaptive Research Trial, Kodumudi.

Most of the grain quality characteristics of ADT41 are comparable with those of Pusa Basmati 1, a high-yielding variety grown in northern India. ADT41 conforms to the minimum acceptable standards for Basmati quality (Table 2),

Table 1. ADT41 (JJ92) yields in Tamil Nadu, India.

Type of trial and year	Trials (no.)	Av grain yield (t/ha)
TNRRI, Aduthurai, 1990-92	4	3.9
Multilocation trial, 1991	4	3.0
Demonstration, at research stations, 1992	8	3.7
On-farm trial, 1992	8	4.6
Adaptive research trial, 1992	20	5.8
Total/mean	44	4.2

Table 2. Morphological and grain quality characters of ADT41 (JJ92).

Character	ADT41	Pusa Basmati 1	Basmati minimum acceptable standard
Plant height (cm)	95	90	-
Days to maturity (d)	110	130	-
1,000-grain wt (g)	24.2	18.8	-
Head rice recovery (%)	55.7	44.8	>40.0
Grain length (mm)	8.3	7.4	6.5
Grain length - breadth ratio	4.3	4.2	3.5
Grain length after cooking (mm)	11.4	12.0	10.0
Grain elongation ratio	1.4	1.7	>1.5
Volume expansion (g/g)	4.6	4.5	3.7
Gelatinization temperature ^a (alkali score)	6	2	5-6
Aroma	Mild	Mild	Fine, appealing smell

^aScored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

with grain length and L-B ratio much higher than the minimum standards. Cooked rice length averaged 11.4 mm. The mildly scented rice is soft and not sticky, making it well-suited for specialty rice products.

The Tamil Nadu State Variety Release Committee has released ADT41 (JJ92) for general cultivation during kharif (monsoon) season in Tamil Nadu. ■

Mahsuri derivatives developed: Kushal, Maniram, Bahadur, and Ranjit

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Kushal, Maniram, Bahadur, and Ranjit have been recommended for flood-free rainfed lowlands during winter season in

Assam. They were developed by crossing Pankaj and Mahsuri. The varieties are free of some of the undesirable traits of Mahsuri. They are fertilizer-responsive and moderately resistant to shattering. Kushal, Maniram, and Bahadur are resistant to blast. Important characteristics and yield data are presented in Tables 1 and 2. ■

Table 1. Main characteristics of varieties.

Character	Kushal	Maniram	Bahadur	Ranjit
Height (cm)	116	105	114	99
Duration (d)	150	150	155	155
Panicle length (cm)	25.8	26.5	27.7	27.5
1,000-grain wt (g)	23.1	21.6	20.2	17.4
Hulling (%)	78.0	79.5	79.0	79.5
Milling (%)	72.0	73.0	71.0	68.0
Head rice (%)	63.0	62.0	64.0	57.0
Amylose content (%)	22.67	20.12	22.71	22.99
Grain length (mm)	5.8	5.6	5.5	5.4
L-B ratio	3.4	3.3	3.6	3.5